

PRINCIPLE CENTERED EFFECTIVENESS AND LEADERSHIP CHARACTERISTICS OF PUBLIC ELEMENTARY SCHOOL HEADS

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Abstract. The study aimed to determine the extent of principle centered effectiveness and the extent of leadership characteristics of public elementary school heads. This study employed a non-experimental quantitative research design utilizing descriptive-correlation method. Validated questionnaire and Universal sampling procedure were utilized considering the minimal number of teachers in the research locale. One hundred twenty (120) public elementary school teachers were the respondents of the study. Using mean, pearson-r, and regression analysis, the findings revealed that the principle centered effectiveness was extensive while the extent of leadership characteristics of public elementary school heads was also extensive. Moreover, the overall results disclosed that indicators for the principle centered effectiveness were positively correlated to the leadership characteristics of public elementary school heads. Further, results from the regression analysis revealed the following have a strong influence of principle centered effectiveness on the leadership characteristics of public elementary school heads: instructional program, learners' personnel administration, and financial and physical support. It is recommended that the school heads should involve the school community in the process of developing a shared vision that aligns with the core values and principles of the school. This collaborative approach encourages ownership, engagement, and commitment from all stakeholders, leading to a more effective and purpose-driven school.

KEY WORDS

1. Principle centered effectiveness.
2. leadership characteristics.
3. instructional program.

1. Introduction

Leadership is a complex phenomenon. A great number of definitions have been offered over the years. Principle-Centered Leadership focuses on individuals and their roles in family life and workplace. Principle-centered leadership leads to long-lasting partnerships rooted in integrity between you and your staff. Through a principle-centered framework of leadership, employees will be self-motivated, teachable, and creative. Principled-centered leaders improve morale and the productivity of their staff. A principle is a fundamental truth or proposition that serves as the foundation for a system of beliefs or behavior or a chain of reasoning. That is a guide for behavior or evaluation. In law, it is a rule that must be or usually is to be followed. Leadership is an explicit inclusion in virtually all business excellence models, but

is not usually defined in a rigorous way, thus model criteria is non-prescriptive. Collectively these accounts imply that systemic leadership requires infusion of core values into people so that they may clearly differentiate between right and wrong. The infusion process is more commonly known as empowerment. Commitment to systemic leadership requires profound trust, a crucial element of which is faith that alternative courses of action filtered through the deployed core values will result in the conscious choice to do that which is right, despite the strength or beauty of attraction promised by any alternative. In global scene, according to Squires (2019), leaders are concerned with the spiritual aspect of their work, that is, they have followers who deeply believe in them, and they possess a latent power in organizations. Principle-centered Leadership discusses that to be successful, effective, and fruitful in any institution, be it at home, business, or church, one must operate based on principles. Principles that “are not invented by us or by society but are the laws of the universe that pertain to human relationships and human organizations. They are part of human condition, consciousness, and conscience.” Principles that will apply “at all times and in all places.” In addition, Davis (2018) states that two important elements of effective school leadership are establishing a school vision and fostering positive interpersonal relationships. He also acknowledges that developing a school vision takes time and the principal should have the ability to determine the status of the school, identify important aspects of improvement and have a contingency plan to solve problems. In addition, they should be knowledgeable about theory and especially those focusing on organizational behavior and leadership. They should possess technical skills needed for managerial responsibilities and the ability to reflect upon their practices in which they skillfully integrate knowledge and skills with experience (Kowalski, 2019). Strong leadership is the cornerstone of all organizations that are able to achieve and maintain long term success. Few organizations are prepared for the challenge. Nearly any business journal or magazine is likely to include an article on the leadership shortage. Whatever the type of organization—government, education, or business and industry it seems that effective leadership is in short supply. The problem is likely to escalate as predicted labor shortages increase. Organizations must take pro-active approaches in the development and retention of leadership talent. They must find ways to prepare their current employees for the leadership challenges of the future. In the Philippines, school heads, which form the core of a school’s leadership team, are increasingly touted as important determinants of school effectiveness. Thus, school heads play a key role as the primary leaders of schools and will greatly influence all aspects of the functions of the schools with their behaviors, personal characteristics, and biases. This view has garnered them added scrutiny in recent educational policy debates over how to improve schools (Sabado, 2018). The best thing about leadership is that we all bring something different from each other. There are no individuals who can express leadership in the same way. Each of us can be a unique leader, and that is why trying to put leadership into a box always fails. If one must read articles on good leadership qualities, one will usually see factors like integrity, effective communication, and influence (Oco, 2022). In Maa District, school heads often lead by example, although it is usually admired in politics, employees prefer a servant leader. They have high integrity and lead with generosity. Servant Leadership style creates a positive culture and high morale among team members. Advocates of the servant leadership model suggest that it is a good way to move ahead and can achieve power because of their values, ideals, and ethics. This style also takes time to apply correctly. It is ill-suited to situations where one must make quick decisions or

meet tight deadlines (Del Valle, 2016).

2. Methodology

This chapter discusses the research methods, which give direction in this investigation. It includes the research design, research respondents of the study, research instrument and the data gathering procedures.

2.1. Research Design—This study used the non-experimental quantitative research design utilizing correlational method. According to Del Valle (2019), descriptive correlational method is used to determine the relationship between two or more variables and to ascertain their relationship. More to the point, Escalante (2022) emphasizes that this method used since the study provides a description of individuals and aims to explain the nature of the data. This study is descriptive in nature since it assessed the principle-centered effective and leadership characteristics of public elementary school heads in Maa District, Division of Davao City. This is correlational since it determines principle-centered and leadership characteristics of public elementary school heads.

2.2. Research Respondents—This study was conducted in seven (7) schools of Maa District, Division of Davao City. The respondents were composed of 120-selected public elementary school teachers of Maa District, Division of Davao City. They have been in the service for at least five to ten years teaching experiences in the Department of Education (DepED) and have said something on the principle-centered effectiveness and leadership characteristics of public elementary school heads. Random sampling technique was employed in this study. However, Langub Elementary School and Magtuod Elementary School with 100 percent of respondents were involved. For the rest of the schools, fifty percent were given the questionnaires. The schools are equidistantly located in the whole district, which can be reached by means of land transportation facilities. The environment is

conducive to educational research.

2.3. Research Instrument—This study used an adapted questionnaire on principle-centered and was patterned from Principle-Centered Leadership of Cove (1989) as cited by Bendor, et. al., (2016). This theory deals with the leadership style focus on principles, one empowers everyone who understands those principles to act without constant monitoring, evaluating, correcting, or controlling. It offers insights and guidelines that can help you apply these principles both at work and at home leading not just to a new understanding of how to increase quality and productivity, but also to a new appreciation of the importance of building personal and professional relationships. The result is a more balanced, more rewarding, and more effective life. This is supported by Hallinger and Murphy as cited by Almedora, et. al., (2016) stating that their model of instructional management by examining the instructional leadership behavior of elementary school principals and reviewing the literature on school effectiveness. This theory deals instructional leadership is leadership that supports the development of teaching and learning. It is referred to using different names including pedagogical leadership, learning-centered leadership, leadership for learning, and learner-centered leadership. The questionnaire was modified mainly through the researcher's preferences to suit the needs of the study. The adapted questionnaire was validated by the experts from the DepEd-Division of Davao City. Validity of the instrument ensured through expert's opinions and pilot testing. To ensure the reliability of the instrument, a

pilot test was conducted through calculating the value of Cronbach’s Alpha with the obtained values of 0.694. The questionnaire was divided into two (2) parts, principle-centered effective and leadership characteristics of public elementary school heads. Hence, the Cronbach’s value of the construct has met the minimum reliability of 0.684, it means that the measures used are consistent enough for the study. In terms of instrument’s face validity, the items were modified to suit the purpose of this study and were validated by experts. The questionnaire was presented to the adviser for comments, corrections,

and suggestions. Part 1 of the questionnaire contained the items on principle-centered effectiveness with the following aspects instructional program, staff personnel administration, student personnel administration and financial and physical resources. Part 2 pertained to the leadership characteristics of public elementary school heads with the dimensions, namely: regard for learning, service orientation, self-energy, and belief in other people. The perceptions of the respondents among the Maa District teachers were based on the following Five-point Likert rating scales:

Range, Descriptive Equivalent, and Interpretation of Principle-Centered Effectiveness

Range	Descriptive Equivalent	Interpretation
4.20-5.00	Very Extensive	The principle-centered effectiveness is always evident.
3.40-4.19	Extensive	The principle-centered effectiveness is oftentimes evident.
2.60-3.39	Moderately Extensive	The principle-centered effectiveness is sometimes evident.
1.80-2.59	Less Extensive	The principle-centered effectiveness is rarely evident.
1.00-1.79	Not Extensive	The principle-centered effectiveness is not evident.

Range, Descriptive Equivalent, and Interpretation of Leadership Characteristics

Range	Descriptive Equivalent	Interpretation
4.20-5.00	Very Extensive	The leadership characteristics are always evident.
3.40-4.19	Extensive	The leadership characteristics are oftentimes evident.
2.60-3.39	Moderately Extensive	The leadership characteristics are sometimes evident.
1.80-2.59	Less Extensive	The leadership characteristics are rarely evident.
1.00-1.79	Not Extensive	The leadership characteristics are not evident.

2.4. Data Gathering Procedure—

1. Permission to conduct study. The researcher wrote a letter asking permission from the Dean of Graduate School to conduct this research study. The researcher secured a permit to conduct the study from the Office of the Schools Division Superintendent of the Division of Davao City through channels to the Office of the Public Schools District Supervisor (PSDS) of the different schools. 2. Distribution and retrieval of questionnaires. Upon approval of the permit to conduct the study, the sets of questionnaires were sent to the respondents via google forms and through email-add of the school heads and teachers. The questionnaires were retrieved right after the respondents were through answering the questions and sent them back through researcher's email-add or messenger. 3. Collection and statistical treatment of data. The data were collected during the Corona Virus Pandemic (COVID-19) time; therefore, the collection of data was based on the protocols set by the Inter-Agency Task Force (IATF) standards. It is a task force organized by the executive of the Philippine government to respond to affairs concerning emerging infectious diseases in the Philippine which was convened in January 2020. The collection of data was conducted following the protocols of IATF to avoid being contaminated and infected by COVID-19. For some participants who missed answering the questionnaire, the video call, via messenger, viber, zoom or goggle meet were used to gather the data or responses of the participants. These were submitted to the statistician for analysis. The researcher together with the statistician tabulated the data, analyzed, and subjected them for statistical analysis.

2.5. *Data Analysis*—The following statistical tools were used in the analysis and interpretation of the responses in this study: Mean. It was used to determine the level of principle-centered and leadership characteristics of public elementary school heads in Maa District, Division of Davao City. Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (Pearson-r). This statistical tool was used in determining the significant components of principle-centered and leadership characteristics of public elementary school heads in Maa District, Division of Davao City. Multiple Linear Regression. This was utilized to determine the significant influence of principle-centered influence leadership characteristics of public elementary school heads in Maa District, Division of Davao City.

3. Results and Discussion

Presented in this chapter were the results of the data gathered. Two sets of research were employed to determine the extent of principle-centered effectiveness and leadership characteristics of public elementary school heads of Maa District, Division of Davao City. The discussion of the results and interpretations were presented accordingly based on the statement of the problems. Presentation of the interpretation was arranged according to the sub-headings: The extent of principle-centered effectiveness in terms of instructional program, staff personnel administration, learners personnel administration, and financial and physical support; the level of leadership characteristics of public elementary school heads in terms of regard for learning, service orientation, self-energy, and belief in other people; and which factors of principle-centered effectiveness significantly influence on the leadership characteristics of public elementary school heads of Maa District, Division of Davao City.

Summary on the Extent of Principle-Centered Effectiveness. Presented in table 1 shows the summary extent of principle-centered effectiveness of public elementary school heads of Maa District, Division of Davao City. The indicator with highest mean is instructional program with a mean of (3.94), interpreted as extensive. It is then followed by financial and physical support had earned a mean of (3.84), which is also identified as extensive. Further, staff per-

sonnel administration had obtained a mean of (3.67) or extensive. Lastly, learner personnel administration has the least mean of (3.57), this also described as extensive. With an overall generated mean of (3.77) or extensive, therefore the summary extent of principle-centered effectiveness was extensive as perceived by public elementary school heads of Maa District, Division of Davao City.

Table 1. Summary on the Extent of Principle-Centered Effectiveness

No	Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Instructional Program	4.00	Extensive
2	Staff Personnel Administration	3.67	Extensive
3	Learner Personnel Administration	3.57	Extensive
4	Financial and Physical Support	3.84	Extensive
Overall Mean		3.77	Extensive

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Summary on the Extent of Leadership Characteristics of Public Elementary School Heads. The summary information on the extent of leadership characteristics of public elementary school heads of Maa District, Division of Davao city is replicated in table 2. The data are presented as follows: Belief in other people had obtained a mean of (4.16) or extensive. Then, it followed Regard for learning has a mean of (4.02) with a description of extensive. In addi-

tion self-energy which gained a mean of (3.91) which also interpreted as extensive. Finally, the respondents on service orientation revealed with a mean of (3.86) which also interpreted as extensive. It an overall generated mean of (3.98) or extensive, therefore the extend of leadership characteristics of public elementary school heads of Maa District, Division of Davao City was extensive.

Table 2. Summary on the Extent of Leadership Characteristics of Public Elementary School Heads

No	Indicators	Mean	Descriptive Equivalent
1	Regard for Learning	4.02	Extensive
2	Service Orientation	3.86	Extensive
3	Self-Energy	3.91	Extensive
4	Belief in Other People	4.16	Extensive
Overall Mean		3.98	Extensive

It can be garnered from the table that belief in other people, regard for learning, and self-energy were extensive. Service orientation was the least among the indicators of leadership characteristics of public elementary school heads. Therefore, a customer’s perception about an organization, its services and quality of service is influenced to a large extent by her interactional experience with employees. The nature of this experience impacts service outcomes like customer satisfaction, customer loyalty, delight, and various other service performance measures. In view of the critical role of employee behaviors in influencing customer and service outcomes, it becomes imperative to identify the factors that drive these behaviors. Research indicates that employees’ performance attributes are impacted by the leadership style prevalent in the organization (May, et. al., 2004) as cited by Popli (2017).

Significant Relationship Between the Principle-Centered Effectiveness and Lead-

ership Characteristics of Public Elementary School Heads of Maa District, Division of Davao City

Shown in Table 3 is the statistical analysis on the significant relationship between the principle-centered effectiveness and leadership characteristics of public elementary school heads of Maa District, Division of Davao City. The overall p-value is equal to 0.000 with an r-value equal to 0.759. This means that there is a strong positive significant relationship between the principle-centered effectiveness and leadership characteristics of public elementary school heads of Maa District, Division of Davao City. Hence, this study rejects its established null hypothesis. The analysis further implies that an increasing manifestation of principle-centered effectiveness by public elementary school heads of Maa District, Division of Davao City leads to an increased manifestation of their leadership characteristics.

Table 3. Relationship Between the Principle-Centered Effectiveness and Leadership Characteristics of Public Elementary School Heads of Maa District, Division of Davao City

Principle-Centered Effectiveness	r	p-value	Decision on Ho
Instructional Program	0.660	0.000	Reject
Staff Personnel Administration	0.524	0.000	Reject
Learner Personnel Administration	0.424	0.000	Reject
Financial and Physical Support	0.634	0.000	Reject
Overall	0.759	0.000	Reject

Particularly, the analysis in Table 3 highlighted also the association between each factor of the principle-centered effectiveness and leadership characteristics of public elementary school heads of Maa District, Division of Davao City. Based on the said analysis, the Instructional Program factor of the principle-centered effectiveness ranked as the top indicator with a p-value of 0.000 and -r-value of 0.660. This result implies that there is a strong positive sig-

nificant relationship between the instructional program and leadership characteristics of public elementary school heads of Maa District, Division of Davao City. This was followed by the Financial and Physical Support factor of the principle-centered effectiveness obtaining a p-value of 0.000 and -r-value of 0.634. Still, this means that there is a strong positive significant relationship between the financial and support and leadership characteristics of public elemen-

tary school heads of Maa District, Division of Davao City. Ranked third is the Staff Personnel Administration factor of the principle-centered effectiveness which obtained a p-value of 0.000 and t-value of 0.524. This means that there is a moderate positive significant relationship between the staff personnel administration and leadership characteristics of public elementary school heads of Maa District, Division of Davao City. Lastly, the Learner Personnel Administration factor of the principle-centered effectiveness which obtained a p-value of 0.000 and t-value of 0.424. This means that there is a moderate positive significant relationship between the learner personnel administration and leadership characteristics of public elementary school heads of Maa District, Division of Davao City.

Regression Analysis on the Significant Influence of the Principle-Centered Effectiveness on the Leadership Characteristics of Public Elementary School Heads of Maa District, Division of Davao City

Shown in Table 4 is the regression analysis on the significant influence of the principle-centered effectiveness on the leadership char-

acteristics of public elementary school heads of Maa District, Division of Davao City. The overall regression analysis obtained a p-value of 0.000 and F-value equal to 44.828 which is higher than the set critical value. This means that the principle-centered effectiveness has a significant influence on the leadership characteristics of public elementary school heads of Maa District, Division of Davao City. This further implies that the regression analysis used in the study is useful which means that there is validity in the interpretation on the assumption of the said influences. Relatively, the regression analysis as presented in the same table shows that there are three (3) out of the four (4) factors of principle-centered effectiveness significantly influenced the leadership characteristics of public elementary school heads of Maa District, Division of Davao City. Therefore, the established null hypothesis of this study that there are no factors of principle-centered effectiveness that significantly influence the leadership characteristics of public elementary school heads of Maa District, Division of Davao City is rejected.

Table 4. Regression Analysis on the Significant Influence of the Principle-Centered Effectiveness on the Leadership Characteristics of Public Elementary School Heads of Maa District, Division of Davao City

Leadership Characteristics		Std. Error	Beta	t	Sig.	Decision on Ho
Constant	1.072	.234		4.558	.000	
Instructional Program	.303	.048	.429	6.323	.000	Reject
Staff Personnel Administration	.075	.057	.098	1.315	.191	Failed to Reject
Learner Personnel Administration	.151	.059	.169	2.572	.011	Reject
Financial and Physical Support	.231	.053	.321	4.362	.000	Reject
R = 0.781, R ² = 0.609, F-Value = 44.828, p-value = .000						

Particularly, these principle-centered effectiveness factors that have significant influenced in accordance to their t-value were the Instructional Program factor which obtained a t-value equal to 6.323 and a p-value equal to 0.000, the Financial and Physical Support factor which obtained a t-value equal to 4.362 and a p-value

equal to 0.000, and the Learner Personnel Administration factor which obtained a t-value equal to 2.572 and a p-value equal to 0.000. On the other hand, the Staff Personnel Administration factor of principle-centered effectiveness does not significantly influence the leadership characteristics of public elementary school

heads of Maa District, Division of Davao City with a t-value equal to 1.315 and p-value equal to 0.191. This numerical rating is considered lower than its set critical value and higher than the set 0.05 alpha value. The regression analysis revealed an R-squared (R²) value of 0.609, signifying that 60.9 percent of the variation in the leadership characteristics among elementary school heads in Maa District, Division of Davao City is attributed to principle-centered effectiveness. In essence, this high (R²) value points to a significant relationship between the leadership effectiveness and the principles they adhere to. This data suggests that principle-centered ap-

proaches are highly influential and should be considered crucial in leadership training and development programs targeted at this demographic. On the flip side, the remaining 39.1 percent of variation in leadership characteristics is not explained by the principle-centered effectiveness variable studied. This leaves room for other factors, not included in the current study, that may have an influential role in determining leadership qualities. These could range from environmental factors, school policies, to personal characteristics like experience or specialized training.

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This section presents the findings of the study based on the data outcome. The conclusions drawn from the findings of the study are likewise outlined in this section. To maximize the significant contribution of this study, the researcher has laid down recommendations in this chapter.

4.1. Findings—This non-experimental research using correlation design in this study aimed to determine the extent of principle centered effectiveness and leadership characteristics of public elementary school heads. Specifically, this study aimed to determine the extent of principle centered effectiveness in terms of instructional program, staff personnel administration, learners' personnel administration, and financial and physical support. Moreover, this also identified the extent of leadership characteristics of public elementary school heads in terms of regard for learning, service orientation, self-energy, and belief in other people. Finally, this study determined the significant relationship between the extent of principle centered effectiveness and the level of leadership characteristics of public elementary school heads. Using non-experimental research, the extent of principle centered effectiveness and leadership characteristics of public elementary school heads was determined. The respondents of the study were the 120-public elementary school teachers in Maa

District, Division of Davao City. A modified teacher-made survey questionnaire was adopted from the study of Principle Centered Effective Cove (1989) as cited by Bendor, et. al., (2016) and Hallinger and Murphy (1985) as cited by Al-mendora, et. al., (2016) was utilized as the main instrument of this study. After thorough analysis, significant findings showed that the extent of principle centered effectiveness in terms of instructional program, staff personnel administration, learners' personnel administration, and financial and physical support was extensive. Similarly, the extent of leadership characteristics of public elementary school heads in terms of regard for learning, service orientation, self-energy, and belief in other was extensive which means that it was sometimes manifested while in terms of leadership characteristics which also extensive. Hence, the extent of leadership characteristics as demonstrated by public elementary school heads of Maa District, Division of Davao City was extensive. The overall p-value is equal to 0.000 with an r-value equal to 0.759.

This means that there is a strong positive significant relationship between the principle-centered effectiveness and leadership characteristics of public elementary school heads of Maa District, Division of Davao City. Hence, this study rejects its established null hypothesis. Finally, indicators of principle centered effectiveness such as instructional program, learners' personnel administration, and financial and physical support have significant influence on leadership characteristics of public elementary school heads.

4.2. Conclusions—Based on the findings of this study, the following conclusions were offered: The extent of principle centered effectiveness of public elementary school heads was extensive. The extent of leadership characteristics of public elementary school heads was also extensive. There was a strong positive relationship between principle centered effectiveness and leadership characteristics of public elementary school heads based on the indicators. Based on the results revealed, the following indicators have a strong influence of principle centered effectiveness to the leadership characteristics of public elementary school heads: Instructional Program, Learners' Personnel Administration, and Financial and Physical Support.

4.3. Recommendations—The following interventions were offered based on the conclusions of the study: Clarify your core values: School heads should clearly define their values and principles that guide their decisions and actions. These values can include honesty,

transparency, respect, and fairness. By clarifying these values, school heads can establish a foundation for principle-centered effectiveness. Foster a positive and inclusive school culture: School heads should create a supportive and inclusive environment where all members of the school community feel welcomed and valued. They can achieve this by promoting open communication, collaboration, and respect among students, teachers, parents, and staff. This can be done through regular meetings, workshops, and professional development programs. Develop a shared vision: School heads should involve the school community in the process of developing a shared vision that aligns with the core values and principles of the school. This collaborative approach encourages ownership, engagement, and commitment from all stakeholders, leading to a more effective and purpose-driven school. Empower and develop teachers and staff: School heads should provide support and professional development opportunities for teachers and staff members. By investing in their growth and well-being, school heads can enhance their effectiveness, job satisfaction, and overall performance. This includes providing them with the necessary resources, training, and feedback to thrive in their roles. Future Researchers may use the findings of this as springboard to conduct a study with a similar subject but with a larger scope to explore other dimensions of the study.

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